

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/colsurfa

On the electrophoretic deposition of Bi_2Te_3 nanoparticles through electrolyte optimization and substrate design

Hazal Batili^{a,*}, Bejan Hamawandi^a, Adem Björn Ergül^a, Muhammet Sadaka Toprak^{a,*}

^a Department of Applied Physics, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, SE-106 91 Stockholm, Sweden

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Thermoelectric
Bismuth telluride
 Bi_2Te_3
Electrophoretic deposition
EPD
Thermoelectric power factor
Seebeck coefficient
Hydrothermal synthesis
Colloidal stabilization
Interface modification
Ligand exchange

ABSTRACT

Assembly of thermoelectric nanostructures with pre-defined morphology and surface chemistry on solid substrates has been one of the challenges for in-plane TE devices. Electrophoretic deposition (EPD) has the potential to be used for this purpose, where the use of non-conductive substrates is required to enable a reliable evaluation of the transport property of electrically active films. Bi_2Te_3 nanoparticles, which were synthesized using microwave-assisted hydrothermal route, were used for the EPD of thermoelectric films on glass substrates. A special substrate was fabricated using maskless photolithography, to evaluate the electronic transport properties of the TE films without the interference of the substrate. Electrolyte composition was optimized for high mobility of the suspended nanoparticles, and Bi_2Te_3 EPD films were fabricated with a high deposition rate, reaching 10 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. Initial EPD films showed high resistivity, ascribed to the surface oxide layer and capping ligands. The resistance was significantly reduced by the addition of a dithiol molecular linker, capable of interconnecting the Bi_2Te_3 nanoparticles through ligand-exchange. Seebeck coefficient in the range -150 to -180 $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ was measured, revealing the transport through the deposited films. Finally, a power factor of 169 $\text{nW}/\text{K}^2\cdot\text{m}$ was estimated, revealing the potential for the application of this technology to large area TE films as active coatings using the developed EPD process.

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: batili@kth.se (H. Batili), bejan@kth.se (B. Hamawandi), adem@kth.se (A.B. Ergül), toprak@kth.se (M.S. Toprak).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2022.129537>

Received 12 May 2022; Received in revised form 17 June 2022; Accepted 18 June 2022

Available online 21 June 2022

0927-7757/© 2022 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Thermoelectric (TE) materials are known for their capability of direct interconversion between heat and electrical power. In the TE materials research, big efforts have been dedicated to the improvement of the figure of merit $ZT = (S^2\sigma T)/\kappa$, where S , σ , and κ are the Seebeck coefficient, the electrical conductivity, the total thermal conductivity, respectively, and T is the absolute temperature. The product of electronic transport properties in the equation ($S^2\sigma$) is defined as the TE power factor (PF) [1]. The most common TE material for room temperature operations up to about 150 °C is $\text{Bi}_{(2-x)}\text{Sb}_x\text{Te}_3$ alloys, where the type of conduction is n-type for Bi-rich compositions and shifts to p-type for Sb-rich compositions [2,3]. TE materials can play a very important role in efficient energy harvesting and recovery. However, they suffer from the disadvantages of low efficiency and high-cost production procedures. The development of scalable synthetic techniques to produce high-quality and reproducible TE materials and devices is critical for the advancement of TE technology. Recent progress has shown that dramatic improvements in the performance of TE devices can be made through the development of nanostructured TE materials. Converting even a small portion of the available waste heat into electricity could contribute towards the reduction of Carbon footprint for energy generation, most importantly, providing a greener steady source of energy. Cost-effective solutions for fabricating high-quality TE films is expected to increase the impact of this technology as a complementary energy harvesting technology.

Assembly of nanostructures with pre-defined morphology and surface chemistry on solid substrates has been required for many different applications in optics, electronics, photovoltaics, biomedicine, and catalysis. Commonly used particle packing mechanisms via solvent evaporation include drop cast deposition [4], spin-coating [5], tape casting [6] and electrophoretic deposition (EPD) [7]. Among these techniques, EPD has the potential of forming films with tunable coverage density and thickness, without the need of external pressure or post processing. It also has the advantages of short processing time, possibility to deposit on complex shaped substrates, and the suitability for mass production [7]. EPD maintains the stoichiometry of the deposited films the same as the starting material since there is no chemical reaction taking place during the deposition. It has been used for the deposition of different material families such as ceramics [8–10], metallic NPs [11–13], biomaterials [14–16], and TE materials [17,18].

In the EPD process, charged particles, suspended or dispersed in a liquid medium, are migrated under the influence of an electric field towards the oppositely charged electrode, and deposited on the substrate surface. After the evaporation of the solvent, a cohesive layer of particles reproduces the shape of the substrate. In electrophoresis, deposition yield and particle packing do not only depend on the stability and particle concentration of the suspension, but also on the aggregation and arrangement of the particles on substrate surface [19].

The kinetics of the EPD process and quality of the deposited film depend on many parameters, which can be divided into two groups: suspension and process parameters [20] (for further details see Supplementary Material, section under EPD). Suspension parameters consist of the physicochemical properties of both the suspended particles and the liquid medium, including particle size and zeta potential of the particles, dielectric constant of the solvent, and the conductivity and viscosity of the suspension. Process parameters are more substrate and setup, related to applied electric field, deposition time, distance between electrodes and conductivity of the substrate. Optimization of these variables is essential and unique for every material for obtaining a high-quality deposition.

Earlier TE films developed by the EPD process were prepared by using 10–20 μm sized commercial particles [17,18], and are deposited on metallic substrates -making it rather difficult to eliminate the effect of the substrate in the transport property evaluation of these films. In this work, we report on the formulation of EPD suspension, using

hydrothermally synthesized NPs of Bi_2Te_3 . In order to eliminate the interference of the substrate with the transport measurements, we fabricated glass substrates via photolithography. After the optimization studies of the EPD process we were able to fabricate Bi_2Te_3 thick films, where the deposited films were homogeneously covering the substrate without any crack formation on the films' surface. Electronic transport properties of the films were evaluated.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

Chemicals used for Bi_2Te_3 synthesis were of analytical grade obtained from Sigma Aldrich (Sweden): Bismuth chloride (BiCl_3 , 98 %), sodium tellurite, (Na_2TeO_3 , 99 %), sodium hydroxide (NaOH , 97 %), ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA, 98.5 %), and sodium borohydride (NaBH_4 , 98 %). BiCl_3 and Na_2TeO_3 were used as the precursors for Bi and Te ions, respectively. Deionized (DI) water was used as the solvent, EDTA as the structure directing agent, NaBH_4 as the reducing agent and NaOH to control the pH of the reaction media.

Ethanol absolute (VWR, 99.8 %), triethanolamine (TEA, Sigma-Aldrich, 99 %), and acetone (VWR, 99.5 %) were used for the preparation of stable EPD suspensions.

In glass substrate preparation, the developer, etchant and remover were AZ 351B, chromium etchant (product no 651826) and AZ 100, respectively, all purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Sweden). Acetone and DI water were used for substrate cleaning. All chemicals were used as received, without further purification.

2.2. Synthesis of Bi_2Te_3

The synthesis was performed in a Milestone flexiWAVE MW system (900-Watt magnetrons for a total of 1800 Watt) as described earlier [21]. One-pot synthesis was achieved by mixing all the precursors in the same media. For the synthesis of Bi_2Te_3 , Bi:Te molar ratio of 2:3 was used. In a 100 ml Teflon vial, BiCl_3 , Na_2TeO_3 , EDTA, and NaBH_4 were mixed where the pH was adjusted to 10.5–11 by the addition of NaOH . Two parallel reaction vessels were used in a single run. The reaction vials were kept under constant magnetic stirring for 30 min to ensure a homogeneous mixing. This was then subjected to MW heating to 220 °C with a ramp time of 4 min and dwell time of 2 min. The solution was then allowed to cool down to room temperature and a clear phase separation was observed with the product settled at the bottom. The particles formed were easily separated from the reaction mixture by centrifuging and were then washed with isopropanol, acetone and water. Thereafter, the powder was dried in a vacuum oven at 60 °C.

2.3. Colloidal characterization

The electrophoretic mobility and conductivity of Bi_2Te_3 particles in DI water, ethanol and acetone were measured using Malvern Zetasizer Nano-ZS90 system. Zeta potential was calculated from the particle mobility using Smoluchowski model for aqueous samples and Hückel model for non-aqueous samples. All measurements were conducted using Malvern Dip Cell Kit (ZEN1002) with a quartz cuvette (Starna Scientific) with 10 mm path length. Separate dip cells were used for aqueous and non-aqueous samples. All the measurements were performed in triplicates and the average values were presented. Detailed characterization of Bi_2Te_3 particles is presented in our previous publication [21].

2.4. Substrate preparation and EPD of Bi_2Te_3

Sheets of stainless steel were used as the counter electrode. All the stainless steel pieces were sonicated with acetone for 5 min to remove the dust particles and surface contamination. The glass substrates, i.e.

the working electrode, were prepared by using Advanced Maskless Aligner (MLA 150, Heidelberg Instruments) which exposes the photo resist in a meander pattern (non-contact) via a focused laser beam ($\lambda = 375$ nm). Substrates were soda lime photo mask blanks ($3 \times 3 \times 0.06$ inch) with low reflective chrome and $0.53 \mu\text{m}$ thick AZ 1500 positive photoresist layers, purchased from G materials. Exposure dose was 140 mJ/cm^2 . After the exposure the substrates were developed for 1 min, etched for 40 s, and kept in a remover bath for a minute. Between these steps it was washed with MilliQ water, and before use it was washed with acetone and DI water. Glass substrates were diced into 25×35 mm pieces for the EPD process but the deposition covered 25×25 mm area on the working electrode. All the patterns for photolithography were designed in KLayout software.

An ideal EPD suspension should have moderately high dielectric constant, low conductivity, and low viscosity to ensure the stability of particles during deposition. Table 1 summarizes physical parameters of the solvents used in zeta potential measurements. The optimization of the NP suspension is necessary to get the maximum yield from the EPD process and to deposit a crack-free and homogeneous film. We tested different combinations and concentrations of ethanol, acetone, and TEA in the suspension to obtain the optimum results from EPD process. The films presented in this paper were prepared by dispersing Bi_2Te_3 particles in a 30 ml solution of ethanol (20 ml), acetone (10 ml) and TEA (17 μl), to obtain a highly charged suspension of 1 wt% Bi_2Te_3 NPs. The resulting suspension was ultrasonicated for 10 min in EMAG 12 HC ultrasonic bath at maximum power at room temperature prior to the EPD process.

EPD experiments were performed by using a Voltcraft CPPS-160–84 power supply in constant-voltage mode. Stainless steel (counter) and glass (working) electrodes were connected to the power supply using alligator clips. The working electrode was connected to the negative and the counter electrode to the positive terminal of the power supply. To connect the Cr lines in the glass substrate a copper (Cu) tape was used. The alligator clip was placed on this Cu tape and after the deposition the Cu tape was removed to disconnect the Cr lines. The electrodes were kept parallel to each other with a separation distance of 15 mm. A glass beaker sitting on a lab jack (stage) was used to contain the EPD suspension. The bottom edges of the electrodes were kept ~ 1 mm above from the bottom of the glass beaker.

After the EPD process, the TE films were spin coated with 1,6-Hexanedithiol (HDT, Sigma Aldrich, 97 %) dissolved in 2-(1-Methoxy)propyl acetate (MPA, Acros Organics, 99 %) to exchange the surface ligands and improve the TE performance of the films. When the films were dry, a strong and highly conductive silver cement (purchased from Micro to Nano, 15-002142) was used to make contacts for transport property measurements.

2.5. Characterization of EPD films

Electronic transport properties were evaluated through the measurement of the Seebeck coefficient (S) and the resistance of the EPD films in the direction perpendicular to the Cr lines on the substrate (Fig. 1). Electrical conductivity (σ) was estimated thereof. Details of the measurement set-up are presented in our previous paper [22]. The S is estimated through the integral method, where one end of the sample is held at a fixed temperature while the other end is heated through the temperature range of interest. In this method TE voltage generated

between the two ends of the sample is registered continuously. The S is given by the slope of the TE voltage vs temperature difference curve, $S = \Delta V/\Delta T$. The transport properties were evaluated at different process steps and the sample designations that are used in the manuscript are detailed below:

- 1) "PGS" - the glass substrate with patterned lines (measured in perpendicular direction to the patterned metallic lines);
- 2) "PGS+HDT" - the patterned glass substrate after the addition of HDT;
- 3) "PGS+EPD#V#m" the patterned glass substrate after the electro-phoretically deposited TE film of Bi_2Te_3 NPs (under #V for #min);
- 4) "PGS+EPD#V#m+HDT" the EPD film after the addition of HDT.

Scanning electron microscopy (FEI Nova 200) was used for micro-structure and thickness evaluation. Several cross-sectional micrographs of the deposited films were taken to determine the film thicknesses.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. EPD media and colloidal stability

Bi_2Te_3 NPs were synthesized using the earlier reported MW-assisted synthesis hydrothermal process [21]. Phase purity of the as-made materials has been studied using XRD and the diffraction pattern shows a high phase purity (see Fig. S1) matched to rhombohedral Bi_2Te_3 (ICDD card no: 015-0863). The resultant particles exhibit hexagonal platelet morphology, as the Bi_2Te_3 crystals grow predominantly along the ab plane direction because the strong covalent bonds between Bi-Te can be easily extended along the plane.

The surface charge, i.e. zeta (ζ) potential, of the particles is a key parameter for determining the stability of the suspension, also the direction and velocity of the particles under the electric field. The interaction between individual particles depends on the electrostatic and van der Waals forces, which directly affects the stability of the overall system. To avoid particle agglomeration, high electrostatic repulsion due to high surface charge is necessary in the EPD process [20]. We performed ζ potential measurements of Bi_2Te_3 particles in water, ethanol and acetone, to study the surface charge of these particles in the three potential solvents (Table 2). The dielectric constants of the solvents, which influences the electrophoretic mobility of the dispersed particles are summarized in Table 1. Bi_2Te_3 particles are hydrothermally synthesized in this work, bearing conjugated ethylenediaminetetraacetate (EDTA) molecules on their surface, which is expected to give them a negative charge at neutral pH, in aqueous media, due to exposed carboxyl groups. The ζ potential analysis show negative charge for NPs dispersed in DI water, in agreement with the surface chemistry. This negative charge with increased magnitude was obtained in ethanol and acetone. To assure the colloidal stability of the suspension, and based on the quality of the films formed in preliminary experiments, a mixture of acetone and ethanol was used as the EPD media, where the addition of a trace amount of triethanolamine (TEA) improved the quality of the deposited films.

3.2. Microstructure evaluation of substrate and EPD films

In order to eliminate the interference of the substrate with the measurements, we designed and fabricated glass substrates via maskless photolithography where the pattern is exposed directly onto the substrate with the help of a spatial light modulator. By using this direct write process, we were able to skip the expensive and time consuming photomask preparation process and all the steps it involves. Two SEM micrographs of the developed substrate are presented in Fig. 2. The lithography process has proven successful by comparing the design and obtained patterns, revealing the feasibility of the adapted exposure and development parameters, leading to $10 \mu\text{m}$ metallic lines on the glass substrate.

Table 1

Physical parameters of the solvents used in zeta potential measurements.

Solvents	Refractive Index (at 633 nm)	Dielectric Constant	Viscosity (cP) (at 25 °C)
Water	1.33	78.5	0.88
Ethanol	1.36	24.5	1.09
Acetone	1.35	20.7	0.31

Fig. 1. Pattern design for photolithography a) the whole glass substrate and a zoomed in section, showing the distance between the Chromium lines and their width, where both are 10 μm . In b) gray rectangles represent the silver contacts for transport measurements and the blue arrows show the direction of measurement.

Table 2

Zeta potential, electrophoretic mobility, and conductivity measurements performed on dispersions of Bi_2Te_3 NPs in water, ethanol, and acetone.

Solvents	Zeta Potential (mV)	Electrophoretic Mobility ($\mu\text{m cm/V s}$)	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S/cm}$)
Water	-8.7 ± 0.7	-0.68 ± 0.3	2.35
Ethanol	-27.2 ± 0.4	-0.36 ± 0.1	0.58
Acetone	-36.8 ± 2.2	-1.44 ± 0.6	0.45

3.3. Optimization of the EPD media

TE films were deposited under different time and voltage conditions at a given electrode separation distance of 1.5 cm. SEM micrographs on

three selected samples are presented in Fig. 3; two samples were deposited at 70 V under 3 (EPD70V3m) and 4 min (EPD70V4m) duration, and one sample was processed at 80 V for 3 min (EPD80V3m). By comparing the two samples prepared under 70 V one can easily see increased thickness of the deposited film by prolonging the process duration; a thickness in the range 2–10 μm was achieved in EPD70V3m, which increased to 15–45 μm in EPD70V4m. This nonlinear increase in the additional minute is attributed to the formation of a continuous film, facilitating further deposition. Increasing the voltage from 70 V to 80 V increases the electric field strength and enables the formation of a more homogeneous film of 30 μm thickness in 3 min (EPD80V3m), though with thickness variations across the film. It is important to note that the substrate coverage of 100 % is obtained in the media mixture developed in this work, as opposed to some earlier reports on having discontinuous

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of the glass substrate with 10 μm metallic lines at different magnifications.

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of EPD films of Bi_2Te_3 NPs, deposited at different voltage and duration.

films with similar mixtures [17].

3.4. Electronic transport properties

Deposited TE films through EPD process were evaluated for their transport properties through the measurement of Seebeck coefficient (S) and electrical resistance. The designed patterned substrates allow us to perform this evaluation reliably, due to enabling the use of glass, i.e. insulator, as the substrate -resolving the conducting substrate problems in earlier works [17,18].

The transport properties of the three films (as EPD70V3m, EPD70V4m and EPD80V3m) are summarized in the Supplementary file, Table S2, and the plots for transport properties of EPD70V3m, EPD70V4m are presented in Fig. S3 and S4, respectively.

The S is measured using the integral method, i.e. by registering the thermovoltage generated through the increase in the temperature of one side of the sample -designated as T_h . Fig. 4a shows the differential thermovoltage (ΔV) generated as a function of the temperature difference (ΔT) for sample EPD80V3m. The change shows an inverse relation to the temperature, due to the dominant type of charge carriers being electrons, as undoped Bi_2Te_3 is an n-type semiconductor. Fig. 4b displays the S as ($\Delta V/\Delta T$) as the function of T_h , where the S starts from $-165 \mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ reaching $-180 \mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ at 303 K ($\Delta T = 25 \text{ K}$). These values are very close to the literature value for this material in its bulk form, (e.g. the reported S for Bi_2Te_3 is between -140 and $-150 \mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ [21]). In all the films presented in this work, the estimated S is found to be in the range -150 to $-180 \mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ (c/o Table S2), revealing the transport through the deposited film, and that the substrate does not contribute to the measured value. In a recent work, a S value of $126 \mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ is reported only upon sintering the EPD film [17], though a higher value is directly attainable in the films developed in this work. As the data on TE films prepared through EPD process is rather scarce, the obtained value is the highest so far for this type of films.

The electrical resistance of the patterned glass substrate (PGS) is found to be open circuit, revealing the insulating character of the substrate. Upon the addition of HDT (PGS+HDT) on this substrate, a resistance value of $1 \text{ M}\Omega$ is measured, suggesting that the molecules can intercalate to form a path between the two terminals. The TE film fabricated via the EPD process (PGS+EPD80V3m) on the patterned substrate also showed open circuit behaviour, attributed to the resistance at particle boundaries. Surface chemistry of these NPs are reported in our earlier work, where the presence of EDTA and oxide layer (Bi_2O_3 and TeO_2) were clearly observed through XPS studies [21], which cause the observed high interfacial resistance. With the addition of HDT into the EPD films (PGS+EPD80V3m+HDT) resistance of about $13 \text{ k}\Omega$ was achieved (Fig. 4c), which is roughly three orders of magnitude lower than the substrate (PGS+HDT). The resistance linearly drops to $11.7 \text{ k}\Omega$ by increasing the hot side temperature (T_h) to 323 K ($50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) (at $\Delta T = 25 \text{ K}$), revealing thermally activated transport behavior of semiconductors. The data reveal a significant reduction in the total measured resistance of the EPD films by the addition of thiolated organic

Fig. 4. Electronic transport properties of EPD80V3m film as a function of the differential temperature (ΔT) or the hot side temperature T_h ; (a) differential thermovoltage (ΔV) vs (ΔT); (b) S vs. T_h ; (c) Resistance vs. T_h , and (d) Calculated power as a function of ΔT (T_c is maintained at $23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/296 \text{ K}$).

molecules, due to improved interconnection of particle boundaries. Thiols are known to interact readily with NPs and are expected to coordinate with the Bi atoms on the surface of Bi_2Te_3 nanocrystals through exchange of surface ligands. There is evidence that dithiol influences the electronic properties of NP films, demonstrated by ethane dithiol treatment of PbS NP films resulting in nearly a tenfold increase in mobility [23]. A similar trend of reduction of resistance was shown recently by the use of single thiols in the organic-inorganic hybrid TE films [22].

Due to the difficulty in precise estimation of the film thickness, (micro)porosity and packing efficiency, it is difficult to accurately calculate the TE power factor. Instead we calculated the maximum generated power by using the measured voltage and resistance values ($P = V^2/R$) for the performance evaluation. The calculated power reaches 2 nW for ΔT of 25 K (Fig. 4d). In a typical TE device, several of these films will be integrated in series, multiplying the power generated. This power, classified as ultralow, can be harvested using power management integrated circuits as a critical component of an ultra-low-power energy harvesting system. Such systems are finding a wide range of applications, such as sensors for industrial as well as consumer use. By taking an average thickness value for the films, the conductivity and the S , the resultant power factor has been estimated; results are summarized in Table S2. A power factor as high as 60 $\text{nW}/\text{K}^2\text{m}$ was obtained for the film with thickness in the range of 25–30 μm thickness, while it was about 160 $\text{nW}/\text{K}^2\text{m}$ for 5 μm thick film. Considering the high deposition rate (about 10 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$) without any vacuum or high tech equipment, obtained values are rather promising, making EPD more attractive for TE applications. The presented films show a high resistance, mostly ascribed to the ligand passivation and surface oxide layers, increasing the interface resistance between the NPs. The energy conversion performance of the films can be enhanced further through thermal treatment, to remove the surface ligands, doping of the films and engineering the interfaces between the NPs, which should lead to improved electrical conductivity.

4. Conclusion

We have presented the electrophoretic deposition of TE films, starting from the synthesis of NP building blocks, formulation of the electrolyte, substrate design, optimization and implementation of the EPD process, as well as the transport property evaluation of the deposited films. A MW-assisted hydrothermal route was used for a rapid synthesis of Bi_2Te_3 NPs. The EPD media was formulated using an organic media mixture, that allowed the fabrication of crack-free films over large areas. A special substrate was designed and fabricated using maskless photolithography, which enabled the evaluation of the electronic transport properties of the TE films more reliably. The EPD films displayed high initial resistance, which was significantly reduced by using dithiol as a molecular linker, increasing interconnectivity of the particles in the films. To the knowledge of the authors, this is the first work developing all the processes using solution based bottom-up routes, eventually leading to potentially promising TE films as coatings. The platform developed here will enable the study of the effect of different molecular linkers, various particle size and morphologies, to obtain the best performing film formulation based on a given composition of the TE NPs. This improved control of film deposition may enable large area applications of TE films as sustainable energy harvesting coatings.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgement

This research has received funding from the Swedish Energy Agency (43521-1) and in part by Swedish Research Council (VR, 2018-03462) and the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under the grant agreement No 863222. The financial support from Olle Engkvist Foundation (SOEB, 190-0315) for the establishment of MW synthesis facilities is highly appreciated. The authors thank Dr. Erik Holmgren for his support in maskless photolithography process.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. **Hazal Batili:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Bejan Hamawandi:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Adem Björn Ergül:** conceived the presented ideas, Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Muhammet Sadaka Toprak:** conceived the presented ideas, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. All authors have read and agreed to the present version of the manuscript. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.colsurfa.2022.129537](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2022.129537).

References

- [1] G. Snyder, E. Toberer, Complex thermoelectric materials, *Nat. Mater.* 7 (2) (2008) 105–114.
- [2] B. Hamawandi, S. Ballikaya, H. Batili, V. Roosmark, M. Orlovská, A. Yusuf, M. Johnsson, R. Szukiewicz, M. Kuchowicz, M.S. Toprak, Facile solution synthesis, processing and characterization of n-and p-type binary and ternary bi-sb tellurides, *Appl. Sci.* 10 (3) (2020) 1178.
- [3] B. Hamawandi, H. Mansouri, S. Ballikaya, Y. Demirci, M. Orlovská, N. Bolghanabadi, S.A. Sajjadi, M.S. Toprak, A comparative study on the thermoelectric properties of bismuth chalcogenide alloys synthesized through mechanochemical alloying and microwave-assisted solution synthesis routes, *Front. Mater.* 7 (2020) 332.
- [4] A. Kumar, Y. Zhang, D. Li, R. Compton, A mini-review: how reliable is the drop casting technique? *Electrochem. Commun.* 121 (2020), 106867.
- [5] Y. Zhang, C. D'Ambra, R. Katsumata, R. Burns, M. Somervell, R. Segalman, C. Hawker, C. Bates, Rapid and selective deposition of patterned thin films on heterogeneous substrates via spin coating, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 11 (23) (2019) 21177–21183.
- [6] R. Krishnan P.P, S. Vijayan, P. Wilson, P. Kumar, K. Prabhakaran, Aqueous tape casting of alumina using natural rubber latex binder, *Ceram. Int.* 45 (15) (2019) 18543–18550.
- [7] L. Besra, M. Liu, A review on fundamentals and applications of electrophoretic deposition (epd), *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 52 (1) (2007) 1–61.
- [8] C.L. Hassam, F. Sciortino, N.T. Nguyen, B. Srinivasan, K. Ariga, F. Gascoin, F. Grasset, T. Mori, T. Uchikoshi, Y. Thimont, et al., Robust, transparent hybrid thin films of phase-change material sb2s3 prepared by electrophoretic deposition, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* 4 (9) (2021) 9891–9901.
- [9] S. Hu, W. Li, W. Li, N. Zhang, H. Qi, H. Finklea, X. Liu, Aqueous electrophoretic deposition of gadolinium doped ceria, *Colloids Surf. A: Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 579 (2019), 123717.
- [10] A. Boccaccini, I. Zhitomirsky, Application of electrophoretic and electrolytic deposition techniques in ceramics processing, *Curr. Opin. Solid State Mater. Sci.* 6 (3) (2002) 251–260.
- [11] S. Yokoyama, I. Suzuki, K. Motomiya, H. Takahashi, K. Tohji, Aqueous electrophoretic deposition of citric-acid-stabilized copper nanoparticles, *Colloids Surf. A: Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 545 (2018) 93–100.
- [12] S. Dor, S. Rühle, A. Ofir, M. Adler, L. Grinis, A. Zaban, The influence of suspension composition and deposition mode on the electrophoretic deposition of tio₂ nanoparticle agglomerates, *Colloids Surf. A: Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 342 (1–3) (2009) 70–75.

- [13] N.T. Nguyen, A. Renaud, B. Dierre, B. Bouteille, M. Wilmet, M. Dubernet, N. Ohashi, F. Grasset, T. Uchikoshi, Extended study on electrophoretic deposition process of inorganic octahedral metal clusters: advanced multifunctional transparent nanocomposite thin films, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.* 91 (12) (2018) 1763–1774.
- [14] A. Boccaccini, S. Keim, R. Ma, Y. Li, I. Zhitomirsky, Electrophoretic deposition of biomaterials, *J. R. Soc. Interface* 7 (suppl.5) (2010) S581–S613.
- [15] C. Dange-Delbaere, C. Buron, M. Euvrard, C. Filiâtre, Stability and cathodic electrophoretic deposition of polystyrene particles pre-coated with chitosan-alginate multilayer, *Colloids Surf. A: Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 493 (2016) 1–8.
- [16] A. Clifford, D. Luo, I. Zhitomirsky, Colloidal strategies for electrophoretic deposition of organic-inorganic composites for biomedical applications, *Colloids Surf. A: Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 516 (2017) 219–225.
- [17] T. Talebi, R. Ghomashchi, P. Talemi, S. Aminorroaya, Fabrication of n-type Bi_2Te_3 film using electrophoretic deposition for thermoelectric applications, *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 343 (2018) 127–130.
- [18] T. Talebi, R. Ghomashchi, P. Talemi, S. Aminorroaya, Thermoelectric performance of electrophoretically deposited p-type Bi_2Te_3 film, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 477 (2019) 27–31.
- [19] R. Moreno, B. Ferrari, Nanoparticles dispersion and the effect of related parameters in the epd kinetics, *Electrophor. Depos. Nanomater.* (2012) 73–128.
- [20] P. Sarkar, D. De, T. Uchikochi, L. Besra, Electrophoretic deposition (epd): fundamentals and novel applications in fabrication of advanced ceramic microstructures, in: *Electrophoretic Deposition of Nanomaterials*, Springer, 2012, pp. 181–215 (pp).
- [21] B. Hamawandi, H. Batili, M. Paul, S. Ballikaya, N. Kilic, R. Szukiewicz, M. Kuchowicz, M. Johnsson, M. Toprak, Minute-made, high-efficiency nanostructured Bi_2Te_3 via high-throughput green solution chemical synthesis, *Nanomaterials* 11 (8) (2021) 2053–2072.
- [22] J. Serrano-Claumarchirant, B. Hamawandi, A. Ergül, A. Cantarero, C. Gomez, P. Priyadarshi, N. Neophytou, M. Toprak, Thermoelectric inks and power factor tunability in hybrid films through all solution process, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 14 (17) (2022) 19295–19303, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.1c24392>.
- [23] E. Klem, H. Shukla, S. Hinds, D. MacNeil, L. Levina, E. Sargent, Impact of dithiol treatment and air annealing on the conductivity, mobility, and hole density in pbs colloidal quantum dot solids, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 92 (21) (2008), 212105.